

MICRO-RAMAN SPECTRA OF Ge–As–Se CHALCOGENIDE AMORPHOUS POWDERS

O. V. Iaseniuc¹, M. S. Iovu¹, A. Ghiulnare², R. Mesterca², A. Jderu², and M. Enachescu^{2,3}

¹*Institute of Applied Physics, Academiei str. 5, Chisinau, MD-2028 Republic of Moldova*
²*Center for Surface Science and Nanotechnology, UPB, Splaiul Independentei 313, Bucharest, Romania*

³*Academy of Romanian Scientists, Bucharest, Romania*
E-mails: oxana.iaseniuc@gmail.com

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Abstract

Analysis of the Micro-Raman spectra of $\text{Ge}_x\text{As}_x\text{Se}_{1-2x}$ ($x = 0.05\text{--}0.30$) amorphous chalcogenide glasses are reported. The Micro-Raman spectra exhibit three main peaks located at about $\nu = 193, 213, \text{ and } 255 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The peaks at around $\nu = 193$ and 213 cm^{-1} can be attributed to the vibrations of GeSe bonds. The presence of the Raman peak at about $\nu = 255 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is attributed to the bond-stretching vibrations of the disordered Se chains and rings. With an increase in the Ge concentration, this peak is shifted to a higher wavenumber due to the shortening of the Se chains. The peak at about $\nu = 300 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is characteristic of the Ge–Ge vibration mode. It is found that the different Ge concentrations slightly change the shape of the Micro-Raman spectra, mainly the intensity ratio.

1. Introduction

In the last decade, interest in amorphous chalcogenide glasses (CGs) has increased due to applications of this material in photonics and optoelectronics. In particular, $\text{Ge}_x\text{As}_x\text{Se}_{1-2x}$ CGs (average coordination number of $Z = 2.1.5\text{--}2.90$) are important for a wide range of technical applications, such as infrared optical elements, acousto-optic and all-optical switching devices, holography, diffractive optics, photonic crystals, etc. [1, 2]. These glasses, such as the Ge–As–Se system, exhibit high chemical stability, fairly high transmission in the IR region, high refractive index, excellent nonlinear properties, low phonon energy, and photo-induced effects [1–4]. Recently, Ge–As–Se CGs have been used as core materials for high-efficiency fiber amplifiers, Raman-parametric lasers, and wavelength converters [5, 6]. It has been found that the physical properties of covalently-bonded glasses are determined by the mean coordination number Z (average number of covalent bonds per atom) [7]. In addition, recently, it has been found that, in the disordered network of the $\text{Ge}_x\text{As}_x\text{Se}_{1-2x}$ glassy system, there exist three distinct phases—floppy, intermediate, and stressed rigid—and the dependence of physical properties on the average coordination number Z [8–10]. It has been shown that some CGs from the $\text{Ge}_x\text{As}_x\text{Se}_{1-2x}$ system, namely, the $\text{Ge}_{0.18}\text{As}_{0.18}\text{Se}_{0.64}$ system, in which the stressed rigid phase exists, can be effectively used as temperature sensors [11]. In addition, according to Mössbauer spectroscopy and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy studies [7] of ^{119}Sn in the $\text{As}_2\text{Se}_3:\text{Sn}_x$ glassy system [12], the introduction of group IV elements of the Periodic Table (Sn or Ge) in arsenic selenide base glass leads to the formation of new tetrahedral $\text{Sn}(\text{Se}_{1/2})_4$ and quasi-octahedral SnSe and GeSe_4

structural units, respectively. In addition, the formation of metal–metal bonds and phase separation in the studied $\text{Ge}_x\text{As}_x\text{Se}_{1-2x}$ and $(\text{As}_4\text{S}_3\text{Se}_3)_{1-x}\text{Sn}_x$ glasses can explain some physicochemical properties [7]. Optical studies, such as infrared reflectance and Raman spectroscopy, are efficient tools for obtaining information on the local structure of the disordered material, especially, when the composition is varied. Analysis of the Raman spectra of binary CGs $\text{As}_x\text{S}_{100-x}$ has revealed the presence of phase separation effects for $x \leq 25$ [13]. It has been shown that doping of chalcogenide glasses with metal impurities shift the main bands to the high frequency region and lead to the appearance of the additional vibration bands in the low frequency spectral range [14–16]. It has been shown that doping of As_2Se_3 with 0.5 at % Dy leads to the appearance of a new additional band in the Raman spectra at $\nu = 185 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, which can be attributed to the formation of new structural units, such as $\text{DySe}/\text{DySe}_2$ [17]. In addition, Raman spectroscopy has been effectively used to study the photo-induced transformation and structural changes during a heat treatment in amorphous As-based thin films. Some results on bulk glasses (optically polished plates) and amorphous thin films of $\text{Ge}_x\text{As}_x\text{Se}_{1-2x}$ have been reported [18]. It has been shown that the Micro-Raman spectra of bulk glasses and thermally deposited amorphous $\text{Ge}_x\text{As}_x\text{Se}_{1-2x}$ thin films consist of one main vibration band situated at about $\nu = 246 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for a lower concentration of Ge and As and is attributed to $(\text{AsSe}_{1/2})_3$ pyramidal units. With an increase in the Ge and As concentrations, this band is shifted to a higher frequency region up to $\nu = 236 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for $x = 0.30$. The vibration mode situated at around $\nu = 205 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is attributed to $\text{Ge}(\text{Se}_{1/2})_4$ tetrahedral units; the intensity increases with increasing Ge and As concentrations. Some shoulders in high-frequency regions at $\nu = 365\text{--}390$ and $500\text{--}530 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, which are attributed to the presence of As–Se bands and Se–Se chains, are also observed.

In this study, we report the experimental results of Raman spectra measurements for powder samples of $\text{Ge}_x\text{As}_x\text{Se}_{1-2x}$ glasses ($x = 0.05\text{--}0.30$, $Z = 2.15\text{--}2.90$).

2. Experimental

Bulk $\text{Ge}_x\text{As}_x\text{Se}_{1-2x}$ ($x = 0.05\text{--}0.30$) CGs were prepared from the elements of 6N purity (Ge, As, Se,) by the conventional melt quenching method. The starting components were mixed in quartz ampoules and then evacuated to a pressure of $P \sim 10^{-5}$ Torr, sealed, and heated to a temperature of $T = 900^\circ\text{C}$ at a rate of $1^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. The quartz tubes were held at this temperature for 48 h for homogenization and then slowly quenched in a furnace.

The Raman studies of the chalcogenide samples were carried out by Confocal Micro-Raman Spectroscopy using a LabRam HR800 system at room temperature. All the Raman spectra were generated by exposing the specimens to a 0.03-mW green laser (wavelength of 532 nm) during 300 s and dispersing the emitted signal onto the CCD detector using a 600 lines/mm grating. The spectral resolution is about 0.6 cm^{-1} . The chalcogenide samples were optically examined using an Axio Observer Inverted Microscope (Zeiss). All the micrographs were recorded in the reflection mode at different magnifications (5 \times , 10 \times , 20 \times , and 50 \times).

3. Results and Discussion

Figures 1 and 2 show the Micro-Raman spectra of the $\text{Ge}_{0.07}\text{As}_{0.07}\text{Se}_{0.86}$ powder samples with a mean coordination number of $Z = 2.21$. This composition with a low Ge concentration is situated in the floppy region [9]. The Micro-Raman spectra of the powder samples consist of four main vibration bands centered at around $\nu = 193, 239, 256,$ and 475 cm^{-1} . The peak around

$\nu = 193 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ can be attributed to the vibration of GeSe bonds (structural units $\text{Ge}(\text{Se}_{1/2})_4$). The peak situated at $\nu = 239 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is attributed to the vibration of $\text{As}(\text{Se}_{1/2})_3$ pyramids [9, 19]. The presence of the Raman peak at $\nu = 256 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is due to the bond-stretching vibration of the disordered Se chains and rings. The peak located in a high frequency region at $\nu = 475 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is associated with the presence of As–Se bands and Se–Se chains.

Fig. 1. Raman spectra of the $\text{Ge}_{0.07}\text{As}_{0.07}\text{Se}_{0.86}$ powder samples.

Fig. 2. Deconvolution of the spectral region marked in Fig. 1.

Figures 3 and 4 show the Micro-Raman spectra of the $\text{Ge}_{0.16}\text{As}_{0.16}\text{Se}_{0.68}$ powder with a mean coordination number of $Z = 2.48$. Note that the composition with a Ge concentration of 16 at % is situated in the intermediate region. It was found that Micro-Raman spectra of the powder samples consist of five main vibrational bands situated at around $\nu = 194, 233, 262, 292,$ and 475 cm^{-1} . As in the case of the $\text{Ge}_{0.07}\text{As}_{0.07}\text{Se}_{0.86}$ powder samples, the peak at around $\nu = 194 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ can be attributed to the GeSe vibrational bonds (structural units $\text{Ge}(\text{Se}_{1/2})_4$). The peak at $\nu = 233 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ shows modes of $\text{As}(\text{Se}_{1/2})_3$ pyramids. The presence of the Raman peak at $\nu = 262 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is attributed to the bond-stretching vibration of the disordered Se chains and rings. The peak located in a high frequency region at $\nu = 475 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ can be caused by the presence of As–Se bands and Se–Se chains.

Fig. 3. Raman spectra of the $\text{Ge}_{0.16}\text{As}_{0.16}\text{Se}_{0.68}$

Fig. 4. Deconvolution of the spectral region

powder samples.

marked in Fig. 3.

Figures 5 and 6 illustrate the Micro-Raman spectra of the $\text{Ge}_{0.25}\text{As}_{0.25}\text{Se}_{0.50}$ powder with a mean coordination number of $Z = 2.75$. This composition is situated in the stressed-rigid region. The Micro-Raman spectra of the $\text{Ge}_{0.25}\text{As}_{0.25}\text{Se}_{0.50}$ powder samples consist of a single broad peak centered at around $\nu = 237 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Some weak peaks in the low frequency region at around $\nu = 192 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and two peaks in the high-frequency region at around $\nu = 259$ and 475 cm^{-1} are identified. The deconvolution process using the Gaussian function of the main peak gives the position of the vibrational modes located at around $\nu = 192, 215, 237, 269,$ and 291 cm^{-1} .

Fig. 5. Raman spectra of the $\text{Ge}_{0.25}\text{As}_{0.25}\text{Se}_{0.50}$ powder samples.

Fig. 6. Deconvolution of the spectral region marked in Fig. 5.

The Micro-Raman spectra of the $\text{Ge}_x\text{As}_x\text{Se}_{1-2x}$ powder samples showed that, with an increase in the Ge concentration, the intensity of the vibrational mode $\nu = 194 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (GeSe bonds) became more intensive, while the peak at $\nu = 230 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\text{As}(\text{Se}_{1/2})_3$ pyramids) decreases in intensity. This case is illustrated in Fig. 7, where the Micro-Raman spectra are summarized for all the powder samples of the $\text{Ge}_x\text{As}_x\text{Se}_{1-2x}$ glassy system. It is evident from the figure that, with an increase in the Ge concentration up to $x = 0.18$ ($Z = 2.54$), the intensity of the vibrational mode $\nu = 195 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (GeSe bonds) increases. According to other measurements [20], studies of the Raman spectra of Ge–Se compounds reveal a decrease in the strength of the Se-chain with the mode centered near $\nu = 260 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and an enhancement in the strength of the vibrational mode around $\nu = 216 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, which indicates the occurrence of a certain phase separation in these materials.

Figure 8 represents the dependence of the wavenumber position of the vibrational modes centered at around $\nu = 193, 236,$ and 255 cm^{-1} on mean coordination number Z . In addition, this figure shows the floppy, intermediate and stressed-rigid phases and their dependences for each region. The same dependences of the peak position of vibrational modes on mean coordination number Z were obtained for the $\text{Ge}_x\text{As}_y\text{Se}_{1-x-y}$ glassy system [21]. It was found that the corner-sharing of the vibrational mode at $\nu = 190 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (tetrahedral units $\text{GeSe}_{4/2}$) is almost constant, when the mean coordination number Z is less than 2.5; however, it slightly decreases to low wavenumbers at $Z > 2.5$, as in our case (Fig. 8, black curve). The disappearance of the vibrational

mode at $\nu = 255 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ means the complete replacement of Se by Ge and by As in $\text{Ge}_x\text{As}_x\text{Se}_{1-2x}$ CGs. The full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the vibrational mode at $\nu = 193 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ increases with an increase in the Ge concentration from 14 cm^{-1} for $x = 0.05$ to 27 cm^{-1} for $x = 0.30$.

Fig. 7. Raman spectra of the $\text{Ge}_x\text{As}_x\text{Se}_{1-2x}$ powder samples. The Ge content is indicated in percents.

Fig. 8. Position dependence of main vibrational modes ($\nu = 193, 213,$ and 255 cm^{-1}) on mean coordination number in the Raman spectra of the $\text{Ge}_x\text{As}_x\text{Se}_{1-2x}$ powder samples.

4. Summary

Bulk (powder) glasses of the $\text{Ge}_x\text{As}_x\text{Se}_{1-2x}$ ($x = 0.05\text{--}0.30$) system with an average coordination number of $Z = 2.15\text{--}2.90$ have been studied and characterized by Micro-Raman spectroscopy. It had been found that the Micro-Raman spectra exhibit three main peaks located at around $\nu = 193, 213,$ and 255 cm^{-1} . The peaks at around $\nu = 193$ and 213 cm^{-1} can be attributed to the vibrational GeSe bonds. The presence of a Raman peak at $\nu = 255 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is due to the bond-stretching of the disordered Se chains and rings.

It has been found that the vibration features of the Micro-Raman spectra change with increasing mean coordination number Z . With an increase in the Ge concentration, the vibration peak at $\nu = 255 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is shifted to a higher wavenumbers due to the shortening of Se chains. The Ge concentration in the glassy system also changes the intensity of the vibrational modes in the Micro-Raman spectra.

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References

- [1] H. Jain and M. Vlcek, *J. Non-Cryst. Solids* 354, 1401 (2005).
- [2] A. Zakery and S.R. Elliot, *J. Non-Cryst. Solids* 330, 1 (2003).
- [3] A. Kovalskiy, J. Cech, M. Vlcek, C.M. Waits, M. Dubey, W.R. Heffner, and H. Jain, *J. Micro/Nanolith. MEMS MOEMS* 8 (4), 043012 (2009).
- [4] I. Blonskyi, V. Kadan, O. Shpotyuk, M. Iovu, and I. Pavlov, *Opt. Mater.* 32, 1553 (2010).
- [5] Z. Rang, V.S. Shiryaev, D. Furniss, L. Sojka, S. Sujecki, M. Benson, A.B. Seddon, and M.F. Chiurbanov, *Opt. Mater. Express* 54 (8), 1722 (2015).
- [6] R. Ahmad and M. Rochette, *IEEE J. Sel. Top. Quantum Electron.* 20 (5), 0900706 (2014).
- [7] R. Golovchak, O. Shpotyuk, M. Iovu, A. Kovalskiy, and H. Jain, *J. Non-Cryst. Solids* 357, 3454 (2011).
- [8] Y. Wang, P. Boolchand, and M. Micoulaut, *Europhys. Lett.* 52 (6), 633 (2000).
- [9] Qu Tao, D.G. Georgiev, P. Boolchand, and M. Micoulaut, *Mat. Res. Soc. Symp. Proc.*, 754, CC8-12 (2003)
- [10] O. Shpotyuk, M. Hyla, V. Boyko, and R. Golovchak, *Physica B* 403, 3830 (2008).
- [11] M. Shpotyuk, D. Chalyy, O. Shpotyuk, M. Iovu, A. Kozdras, and S. Ubizkii, *Solid State Phenom.* 200, 316 (2013).
- [12] P. Boolchand, D. Georgiev, and M. Iovu, *Chalcog. Lett.* 2 (4), 27 (2005).
- [13] T. Wagner, S.O. Kasap, M. Vlcek, A. Sklenar, and A. Stronski, *J. Mater. Sci.* 33, 5581 (1998).
- [14] M.S. Iovu, E.I. Kamitsos, C.P.E. Varsamis, P. Boolchand, and M. Popescu, *J. Optoelectron. Adv. Mater.* 7 (3), 1217 (2005).
- [15] A.V. Stronski, M. Vlcek, A.I. Stetsun, A. Sklenar, and P.E. Shepeliavyi, *J. Non-Cryst. Solids* 270, 129 (2000).
- [16] M.S. Iovu, S.D. Shutov, A.M. Andriesh, E.I. Kamitsos, C.P.E. Varsamis, D. Furniss, A.B. Seddon, and M. Popescu, *J. Optoelectron. Adv. Mater.* 3 (2), 443 (2001).
- [17] M.S. Iovu, E.I. Kamitsos, and C.P.E. Varsamis, *Mold. J. Phys. Sci.* 3 (3–4), 286 (2004).
- [18] M.S. Iovu, O.V. Iaseniuc, D. Dinescu, and M. Enachescu, in *Proc. SPIE 10010, Advanced Topics in Optoelectronics, Microelectronics, and Nanotechnologies VIII*, M. Vladescu R. Tamas, I. Cristea (Eds.), p. 100100 (2016).
- [19] Y.-L. Gan, L. Wang, X.-Q. Su, S.-W. Xu, X. Shen, and R.-P. Wang, *J. Raman Spectrosc.* 45, 377 (2014).
- [20] P. Boolchand, M. Jin, D.I. Novita, and S. Chakravarty, *J. Raman Spectrosc.* 38, 660 (2007).
- [21] R.P. Wang, A. Smith, A. Prasad, D.Y. Choi, and B. Luter-Davis, *J. Appl. Phys.* 106, 043520 (2009).